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Looking for the bioclimatic envelopes of SARS CoV-2: if any, here be dragons

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Highlights:

- Weather explains a little of the space-time dynamics of SARS CoV-2
- Bioclimatic envelope models cannot explain the non-stationary anthroposphere
- Transmission routes in outdoor and indoor environments need clarification
- COVID-19 pandemic outbreaks should study by using multi-scale analysis
- Epidemiological geography reveals multiple social and cultural drivers

Abstract

We addressed the effects of atmospheric conditions on the spread of the SARS CoV-2 coronavirus and its associated disease, COVID-19; we also assessed the limitations of bioclimatic envelopes on the geographic distribution of SARS CoV-2. There is a wide consensus that the global distribution of COVID-19 is not random but conditioned by environmental drivers. Researchers agree that weather and/or climate influence the

25 distribution of COVID-19: a cool and dry environment seems to be the most suitable for
26 the spreading of SARS CoV-2. However, as the COVID-19 distribution becomes
27 global, including tropical climates, the evidence reveals that atmospheric conditions
28 explain, at most, only a limited amount of the space-time dynamics of SARS CoV-2.
29 Thus, the usefulness of approaches based on bioclimatic envelopes is in question. There
30 are uncertainties behind the spread of SARS CoV-2. Atmospheric conditions may have
31 some influence, directly or indirectly, but the dominant route for the spread of COVID-
32 19 is the non-stationary environment of the anthroposphere. We contend that there is
33 unexplored and potentially dangerous territory; hence, here be dragons.

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36 **Keywords:** COVID-19; weather; climate; correlative models; anthroposphere.

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40 **1. Introduction**

41 On 11 March 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) declared the outbreak of the
42 COVID-19 disease caused by the novel coronavirus SARS CoV-2 to be a global
43 pandemic (WHO, 2020). From the beginning, authors have highlighted the potential
44 influence of atmospheric conditions on the distribution of SARS CoV-2 and the spread
45 of the COVID-19 disease. Most of the contributions concluded that there is some
46 influence of weather and/or climate on the spread of COVID-19 (Al-Rousan and Al-
47 Najjar, 2020; Bashir et al., 2020; Holtmann et al., 2020; Ma et al., 2020; Sajadi et al.,
48 2020; Tobías and Molina, 2020; Xie and Zhu, 2020). Specifically, a cool and dry
49 environment in a mesothermal climate seems to most favour the spread of the SARS
50 CoV-2 coronavirus. This perception became a mantra during the early stages of the
51 COVID-19 pandemic. So, it appeared in many research papers based on the relationship
52 between climate suitability of SARS CoV-2 and the COVID-19 pandemic spread risk,
53 some of which showed extrapolations in space-time (Araújo and Naimi, 2020; Coro,
54 2020; Scafetta, 2020).

55 However, other researches questioned the effect of atmospheric conditions and the
56 importance of these variables to explain the COVID-19 pandemic outbreaks across
57 multiple scales (Briz-Redón and Serrano-Aroca, 2020; Jüni et al., 2020; O'Reilly et al.,
58 2020; Pacheco et al., 2020). Some review papers also questioned the existence of a
59 significant genuine effect of atmospheric conditions (Brassey et al., 2020; Gutiérrez-
60 Hernández and García, 2020; Mecenas et al., 2020).

61 On old maps, the expression 'Here be dragons' (from the Latin, *Hic sunt dracones*)
62 indicated that which lay beyond the world as it was known, and they often showed
63 fantastical creatures (e.g., dragons) that served as indicators of the limits of our

64 knowledge (Van Duzer, 2012). As such, this means that unexplored territories are
65 potentially dangerous.

66 In this paper, we address the uncertainties about the spread of the COVID-19 disease
67 and the limitations of bioclimatic envelopes in the geographical distribution of SARS
68 CoV-2. We discuss some key points paramount to understanding the research problem
69 posed to the geographical distribution and spread of the COVID-19 pandemic. Namely,
70 SARS CoV-2 *vs.* COVID-19, weather *vs.* climate and models *vs.* anthroposphere.
71 Concerning the influence of atmospheric conditions (and other candidate drivers) on the
72 disease distribution, we hypothesise that extrapolations in space-time do not add
73 explanatory power to future scenarios of the COVID-19 pandemic.

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75 **2. Discussion**

76 ***2.1. SARS CoV-2 vs. COVID-19***

77 SARS-CoV-2 is the name of the virus (severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus
78 2), and COVID-19 refers to the coronavirus disease (China Medical Treatment Expert
79 Group for Covid-19, 2020; Wu et al., 2020). It is crucial to distinguish between the
80 virus and the disease because research mistakes derive from this misperception.
81 According to experimental studies, the stability of SARS-CoV-2 depends on
82 temperature and humidity: the virus is highly stable at 4°C, but sensitive to heat (Chin et
83 al., 2020). Aerosol and fomite transmission of SARS-CoV-2 is plausible since the virus
84 can remain viable and infectious in aerosols for hours and on surfaces for up to days
85 (van Doremalen et al., 2020). These are the principal sources of evidence about the
86 hypothesis that relate the role of the environment on the incidence of COVID-19.
87 However, SARS-CoV-2, in controlled environments on the human transmission of

88 COVID-19 is largely unknown, and other factors may also determine the incidence of
89 COVID-19. It is not realistic to consider outdoor temperature and relative humidity as
90 driving factors of the COVID-19 incidence (Passerini et al., 2020). Most of the research
91 that associated weather variables with the spread of COVID-19 were retrospective
92 observational studies. Based on a systematic review, Mecenas et al. (2020) observed
93 homogeneity in the findings regarding the effect of temperature and humidity on the
94 seasonal viability and transmissibility of COVID-19. In this systematic review, the
95 authors reviewed seventeen studies and performed a quality assessment. They found
96 four studies that had a high risk of bias and another thirteen with a moderate risk of
97 bias. They also assessed the certainty of the overall evidence as low, both for
98 temperature and humidity factors.

99 **2.2. *Weather vs climate***

100 Weather is the state of the atmosphere and its short-term variation in minutes to weeks;
101 climate is the weather of a region over a long time, 30 years has been established by
102 convention (Barry and Chorley, 1968). Climate information includes statistical analyses
103 about the normal weather and the range of weather extremes for a location or region.
104 Here, it is also crucial to distinguish between the scales of weather and climate. Many
105 researchers have suggested that the optimal conditions for increasing the transmission of
106 SARS CoV-2 are a cool, dry environment in a mesothermal climate, which this might
107 lead a seasonal component to the pandemic (Baker et al., 2020; Sajadi et al., 2020).
108 Araújo and Naimi (2020) suggested that the environment can mediate human-to-human
109 transmission of SARS-CoV-2 and that unsuitable climates can cause the virus to
110 destabilise rapidly, hence reducing its capacity to become epidemic. According to Baker
111 et al. (2020), variations in weather may be important for endemic infections, but during

112 the pandemic stage of an emerging pathogen, the climate drives only modest changes.
113 In this sense, Baker et al. (2020) suggest that, after the initial pandemic phase, endemic
114 cycles of the disease will probably be linked to climate drivers. However, at present,
115 SARS CoV-2 is in an active propagation phase; therefore, it is incorrect to assume that
116 its current distribution is in an equilibrium with climate.

117 Bioclimatic envelope models are correlative models exploring the relationship between
118 species occurrences and environmental predictors (Araújo and Peterson, 2012). The
119 simplest approach to model ecological niches is by fitting bioclimatic envelopes and
120 identifying shapes in multidimensional environmental space that enclose environments
121 that are associated with known occurrence localities (Peterson et al., 2011). One of the
122 most controversial assumptions of the bioclimatic envelope models is that species
123 distributions will be at equilibrium with the climate; this means that species inhabit the
124 entire spatial footprint of their habitable conditions (Václavík and Meentemeyer, 2012).
125 When applying the bioclimatic envelopes in static species distribution modelling
126 without including dynamic elements, the underlying assumption is that species are in
127 quasi-equilibrium with contemporary environmental conditions (Franklin, 2009).
128 However, the distribution of SARS-CoV-2 is not in equilibrium with climate, and
129 correlative models are inappropriate for explaining and predicting the spread of
130 COVID-19 (Carlson et al., 2020a; Chipperfield et al., 2020).

131 According to Araújo et al. (2020), correlative models can provide insight concerning the
132 environmental persistence of SARS-CoV-2; they propose that this insight may explain
133 the spread of the disease. However, their models have changed over time (Araújo and
134 Naimi, 2020), and no bioclimatic niche has been found. COVID-19 seems to have spread
135 globally, unencumbered by climate, but correlative modelling efforts continue to search

136 for a climate signal (Carlson et al., 2020b). At present (30 July 2020), according to the
137 real-time data from Johns Hopkins University (Dong et al., 2020), the COVID-19
138 pandemic projects a global wave. Therefore, there is no clear evidence that the COVID-
139 19 pandemic has seasonal behaviour. In other words, the COVID-19 seasonal behaviour
140 is still unknown and unpredictable, at least on a global scale in this stage of the
141 pandemic wave. Here certainly be dragons.

142 ***2.3. Models vs anthroposphere***

143 To model the space-time dynamics of COVID-19, it is crucial to consider the non-
144 stationary nature of the anthroposphere.

145 Most of the bioclimatic studies about COVID-19 are based on correlational models, in
146 which they interpret the resulting correlations as evidence of causal links (Currie et al.,
147 2019). Correlative models (similar to bioclimatic envelope models) transfer the
148 suitability of human transmissions of SARS-CoV-2, assuming an inadequate space-for-
149 time substitution assumption (Damgaard, 2019). They use static models in non-
150 stationary environments, and the results can lead to erroneous conclusions because
151 epidemiological processes occur in time.

152 We relate another limitation to the data. Omori et al. (2020) illustrate how epidemic
153 curves of reported cases may not always reflect the true epidemic growth rate due to
154 changes in testing rates. The limited diagnostic testing capacity could influence data
155 during the early epidemic phase. This generates unknowns related to the prevalence of
156 COVID-19 over time. In this sense, serological surveys are a valuable tool to assess the
157 extent of the epidemic, given the existence of asymptomatic cases and low access to
158 diagnostic tests (ENE-COVID Study Group, 2020). However, testing and reporting of

159 COVID-19 differs across reporting units and is constantly changing; this makes the
160 comparison between different periods and space units difficult (Malanson, 2020).

161 Many studies suffer from inadequate research designs that do not address critical issues
162 such as brief time series, serial and spatial autocorrelation, clustering, spurious
163 correlations, problems of multicollinearity and inadequate analysis scales (Carlson et
164 al., 2020a; Chipperfield et al., 2020; Malanson, 2020; Mecenias et al., 2020). All of
165 these issues make it difficult to isolate a genuine effect of atmospheric conditions on
166 disease spread from any other effects, including potential artefacts derived from
167 observed prevalence, spatial dependence, temporal dependence and human geography
168 (Gutiérrez-Hernández and García, 2020). However, more research is necessary to
169 clarify the modes of virus transmission, evolution, mutation and the direct and indirect
170 mechanisms of contagion (Eslami and Jalili, 2020).

171 The anthroposphere is the portion of the environment where human activities make up a
172 significant source of change (Kuhn and Heckelei, 2010). Cultural habits,
173 epidemiological knowledge and public health interventions will decisively determine
174 the state and change of the COVID-19 pandemic. Therefore, the anthroposphere is a
175 non-stationary environment. Although several authors have suggested that seasonal
176 forcing on SARS- CoV-2 should be taken into account in the further monitoring of the
177 global transmission (Neher et al., 2020), we think the COVID-19 pandemic overflows
178 the climate determinism. Not that climate drivers are not relevant to processes like
179 aerosol transmission, but their influence may be partial and confounded by human
180 behaviour and the microclimate of built environments (Carlson et al., 2020a).

181 In this sense, early healthcare measures (e.g. social distancing) are more powerful than
182 the later ones (Ortega-García et al., 2020), so it is possible to mitigate the potential

183 seasonal climate effects. Public health interventions are crucial to reducing epidemic
184 growth over climate drivers (Jüni et al. (2020).

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186 **3. Concluding remarks**

187 Atmospheric conditions may explain a limited amount of the space-time dynamics of
188 SARS CoV-2. However, most studies are based on correlative models with weak
189 statistical and theoretical foundations. Additionally, bioclimatic envelope models are
190 not adequate to explain the non-stationary context of the anthroposphere, at least in the
191 early stages of the COVID-19 pandemic. In any case, their results should be interpreted
192 with caution, avoiding extrapolation. It is also necessary to clarify the role of the
193 different transmission routes at multiple scales and in outdoor and indoor environments.
194 Atmospheric conditions may have some influence on the spread of COVID-19, directly
195 or indirectly, but the dominant route is the non-stationary environment of the
196 anthroposphere.

197 Since atmospheric conditions may only explain a very limited amount of the space-time
198 dynamics of SARS CoV-2, until we find the bioclimatic envelopes of SARS CoV-2, if
199 any, here be dragons. We have to be careful about reporting this because it could lead to
200 dangerous and unforeseen consequences. It is important to realise the amount of risk we
201 take when we report interim results that have not been subjected to peer review. Science
202 is not a heuristic game. Incorrect extrapolations can have pernicious consequences for
203 the credibility of science and public health, particularly if the media and official
204 institutions echo them.

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